

APPLICATION OF THE 12 IDEAS OF MS. PATTI DRAPEAU IN THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM IN THE CROSS-SECTION OF SCIENCES ON THE EXAMPLE SUBJECT OF READING LITERACY IN PRIMARY GRADES

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Annotation: The article covers the information about Ms. Patti Drappeau and her 12 ideas, “Stop and start” as well as the use of these ideas in order in literature subjects in primary education.

Keywords: Patti Drappeau, Stop and Start, 12 ideas and their names, third grades reading literacy, true friend, Uzbek proverbs, different questions, cards, “T” table, debate questions.

Ms. Patti Drappeau is a creative consultant, distinguished presenter, and trainer in the American field of education. Her presentations and promoting themes are based on creativity and teaching strategies.

Her 12 ideas for "Stop and start" include:

1. Elementary questions.
2. questions of different categories
3. Opposite mental attack strategy.
4. Voice and sound effects
5. Work with cards.
6. Connect and find a solution to the problem.
7. Variable matrix.

8. What does it mean?
9. A new and unusual product.
10. Feel.
11. Lost and recovered.
12. Point of view.

Now I want to highlight these 12 ideas on the basis of a story taken from the subject of 3rd grade reading literacy. The title of the story is "True Friend."

Not in ancient times, one of the days when we lived, the cars produced in our own country were on the road from all sides. Cars that are in love with the destination from different edges of the land meet on the same road as fate dictates and go back and forth. At one point, the cars stopped at the foot of a tree to rest. Then the three cars argued: "I am stronger than both of you," the big car said. "I walk on the mountain, in the snow, in the city everywhere without difficulty. My height is tall; my respect and reputation are higher than all of you," she said with vaunt. "Swim the eyes of a beautiful tall car who observed the event: You know that I am beautiful to everyone, although you will not admit it. In fact, each of all the cars covers me," he said. "But all cars did not hear her words. The third car was silent. "Time will tell who is who," he quietly leaves. All three cars were on the road again, and the road was running in abundance. Meanwhile, the fuel of the proud big car was reduced. Angered by this, the car stops and starts walking. And the noble car, as if it were a great one, passed by as far as the lip was twisted. The third car came to near the big car and helped him. Then he poured the fuel from his reserve into a big car. He did not hide his regret. They set off again. The car finished her water, which liked the clarity of her windows. However, although he was angry, he preferred to leave the cars to not ask for help so rash. The third car forgets her words and gives him water. Happy with this, Car quickly washed his face and looked at his beauty again. Then the big car went out in front of the third car and said so: My friend, forgive us; in fact, you are

the strongest, humblest, and kindest in the us.The second car also tilted its head.Forgive me when we break your heart," said.A modest, kind car continued on its way,

1. Elementary questions.

What do you think the author put forward through the story?

Why did the third car not behave like other cars?

How do you describe the heroes of the story?

Can the three cars be called true friends? Why?

2. questions of different categories

What kind of work would you like to repeat if you became the heroes of the story? Why?

How do people behave if the situation in the current story occurs in our lives?

What to do to lose habits like conceit and bragging?

3. Opposite mental attack strategy.

What would happen if the third car did not help the other cars?

What would happen if the big and beautiful car continued in this habit again without asking for forgiveness, not realizing that the third car was humble and kind?

4. Voice and sound effects

3 students come out in front of the whiteboard. Three are put on a mask with the image of 3 different cars. The same story is performed with suitable voices as a stage appearance.

5. Work with cards.

6. Connect and find a solution to the problem.

The two friends are severely tightened. The situation became more severe, and they went into a state of not talking to each other. Both are your friends. You're stuck in the middle of two. What would you do in this situation?

On the street, you saw bully children beating a child and laughing over them by taking a bag and throwing down the items inside on the way. How do you behave in this situation?

7. variable Matrix.

"T" jadvali

Manmanlik Yomonlik	Kamtarlik Yaxshilik
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8. What does it mean?

9. A new and unusual product.

Continuing the story...Students are given time to think freely. During this time, they make changes to the story, add new characters, and add new situations.

10. Feel.

1. What would you feel when you were in the place of the car?

2: What would you feel when you were in the place of the car?

3: What would you feel when you were in the place of the car?

11. Lost and recovered. Uzbek proverbs

.....ga kamol,

.....ga zavol.

..... - el g`amida

Yomon:... g`amida.

Yaxshi, yursang, yetarsan,

..... yursang qolarsan....

12. Point of view

Are there many advantages to being friends with parents or with peers around?

In conclusion, if teachers use these ideas of Mrs. Patti drappeau, teachers can organize an unusual lesson and increase their activity by taking students interested in the lesson. As a result, the student can easily find his way in the future by studying science perfectly. The application of these ideas throughout the course in various subjects teaches students to think, find solutions to problems, creativeness, and comparison.

List of used literature:

1. Ms. Patti Drappeau: “Sparking student creativity”
2. Ms. Patti Drappeau: “Great teaching with graphic organizers.”
3. Ms. Patti Drappeau: “Differentiated Instruction Making It Work”
4. The reading literacy book for third grades
5. The presentation of “Stop and Start” by Kimyo International University`s teacher.